

Employability of Saint Paul University Surigao Criminology Graduates from 2013 To 2020

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Abstract --- *In evaluating the long-term effects and efficacy of educational programs across multiple sectors, tracer study research is crucial. It offers priceless insights on the outcomes and trajectories of graduates, illuminating their chances of finding work, enjoying their jobs, utilizing their skills, and making contributions to society. This study aimed to trace and determine employment status of Criminology graduates from 2013 to 2020 of Saint Paul University Surigao (SPUS). It utilized quantitative-descriptive research design anchored from the Tracer Study of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Graduates of SPUS using questionnaire from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) tracer study. Seventy-one (71) criminology graduates were purposefully chosen as respondents of the study. Data were gathered via online platforms such as email, messenger, and among others. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools and some parametric tests. It was shown that out of 71 respondents, 43 were able to secure a job related to the course they graduated in. Furthermore, results revealed that SPUS provided quality learning that has become effective in the graduates' pursuit of profession. It was revealed also that the institution presented comprehensible and understandable information which relates to real-life situations, instilled values for them to become competent learners and believers, showed how participation in the school's religious activities have contributed to their development, and provided updated learning resources necessary for academic references. Hence, the researchers recommend that the institution reinforces the importance of improving teaching skills as part of their commitment to professional excellence through the establishment and support of campus resources.*

Keywords --- *tracer study, effectiveness, quality teaching, student activities engagement, learning environment, student support services.*

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Higher education institutions serve as key pillars of human growth and a strong force for both individuals and society. A tracer study is an essential instrument that can offer useful information for tracking graduates and determining their employment status. Criminology students can advance their studies and abilities by knowing about the educational backgrounds or track studies of criminology graduates. This study is very helpful in giving the institution early input on the employment situation of their graduates so that improvements in the curriculum can be made for the benefit of future graduates.

Graduate tracer studies contribute to the program's continued relevance. Graduate tracer studies are one form of empirical study that can appropriately provide valuable information for evaluating the results of the education and training of a specific institution of higher education. It can collect essential information concerning the employment profile of graduates, their undergraduate experience, the first and current jobs of graduates and the relevance of their educational background and skills required in their job. Tracer studies play a vital role in gathering information on the curriculum's applicability and graduates' level of satisfaction with their academic preparation (Woya, 2019).

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In the challenges of 21st century education, higher education stands out as one of the major keys to cope with reforms through instruction, research, and extension. It has become a big challenge for all Philippine Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to cater these reforms. According to the Tertiary Education Commission, one method to address these concerns is by producing graduates who are fully ready to take what they have learned in school and apply it to their respective works (Cuadra et al., 2019). Thus, this present study proposes to trace the graduates of criminology department for the academic years 2013 to 2020 including information as to their employability.

The College of Criminal Justice Education of St. Paul University Surigao provides the student foundation, just like every academic institution that aspires to create graduates who are capable and well-educated and who will eventually be able to compete on a local and international level. An extremely effective approach for assessing the locations and performance of graduates in the workplace is a graduate tracer study (Cuadra et al., 2019). This research will seek to trace and determine the employability status of criminology graduates from 2013 to 2020. Employability plays an important role in the implementation of the departments' learning and teaching strategies. It is part of good learning practice. Students who engage in developing their employability are likely to be independent, reflective, and responsible learners (Ruiz et al., 2020).

The purpose of this research is to gather data and trace criminology graduates, and to determine their employment status. R.A. 7722 mandates the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to "monitor the performance of the programs and institutions of higher learning". One way to do this is to conduct a graduate tracer study looking at the employability of the graduates. Further, tracer study is a requirement for accreditation and certification initiatives of the school to ensure quality standards. With this, the researchers propose to conduct this graduate tracer study of a Bachelor of Science in Criminology of Saint Paul University Surigao. The result of the study will provide important inputs to further improve its curriculum, and other related activities.

1.2 Objectives

This study aimed to answer the following specific questions:

1. What are the profiles of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, year graduated, location, and professional examination(s) passed?
2. What is the employment information of the respondents in terms of employment status, reason for unemployment, present occupation, affiliation, first job relatability to the course, reason for accepting the first job, and duration of the first job?
3. What is the respondents' rating of their program in terms of quality of teaching, student activities engagement, learning environment, and student support activities?
4. Is there a significant difference of the respondents' rating of their program when grouped based on their employment information?
5. What is the overall rating on the effectiveness of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curricular program?

1.3 Literature Review

A graduate tracing study or often known as a tracer study is a study of graduates of a university. The results of this tracer study can be used to evaluate an educational program. Alumni are at the forefront of the study program to always encourage them to always look ahead while at the same time attracting their younger generation to participate and feel their success. Alumni are the determinants of quality in teaching and learning activities at the University, both the quality of teachers, namely lecturers, and the quality of education staff (Hasibuan et al., 2022). A tracer study is defined as an impact assessment tool where the impact on the target groups is traced back to specific elements of a project or program so that effective and ineffective project components may be identified (Gines, 2014). In educational research, the tracer study is sometimes referred to as a graduate or alumni survey since its target group is former students. They provide quantitative-structural data on employment and career, the character of work and related competencies, and information on the professional orientation and experiences of their graduates. Biographical data on "Where are our graduates now?" may supply information on income, job title, nature of employment, and years of employment as mentioned in the study of (Herrera, 2017).

Employability

Bates et al. (2019) defined graduates' employability as an individual's capacity and willingness to

become and remain attractive in the labor market and be successful in a wide range of jobs is becoming a major research theme. Accordingly, employability shows having the knowledge, understanding, skills, experience, and personal attributes to move self-sufficiently within the labor market and to realize one's potential through sustainable and fulfilling employment experiences throughout the course of one's life. Furthermore, Gill (2020) defined employability skills as a set of achievements that graduates develop – skills in understandings and personal attributes – that make them more likely to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupation, benefiting themselves, the workforce, the community, and the economy.

There is some confusion regarding the concepts of employability and employment, even though they are very different. As emphasized in the study of Bates and Hayes (2017), employment involves an individual holding a job while employability is when an individual is capable of being employed. A person can be highly employable while not holding a job for reasons such as family commitments. Additionally, employability is a complex concept that is continually evolving. Research suggests that employability contains subareas: collaboration and teamwork, informed decision making, information literacy in context, commencement readiness, lifelong learning, professional practices, and standards as well as integration of theory and practice. It was argued also that employability has broader factors including social capital (e.g., networks, social class, and university ranking), human capital (e.g., skills, competencies, work experience), individual behaviors (e.g., career self-management, career building skills) and individual attributes (e.g., personality factors, adaptability, flexibility). Students are aware that, in conjunction with their educational institution, they have some responsibility for their employability. Various factors affect students' perceived employability including their prior work experience and particular types of work-integrated learning. As well as through placements, employability can be enhanced through simulations and work experience within the field that they are studying, working outside the field that they are studying, volunteering and being members of student clubs. Research suggests that there are six curriculum elements within a work-integrated learning course that contribute to the students' employability. These are authenticity, preparation, supervision, debrief, activities focused on integration and assessments focused on integration.

Accordingly, competitive graduates in the job market often depend on a strong curriculum of the programs. Graduates are competing among themselves to meet the job market in various sectors (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020). Because of the limited number of jobs available, many graduates end up unemployed. In the 21st century, employability skill is the most required skill besides technical knowledge to compete for employment and sustain a job at the industrial global market. Schools must provide the training that meets the standards employers set for their workforce. Industries may have different standards, but they always have a set of characteristics they expect their applicants to possess that would boost institutional objectives. Whether employers seek graduates whose skills are, either, related or not aligned to their field of specialization, they will always look for their standards.

The unemployment rate in the Philippines in January 2019 was estimated at 5.2%. "Of the total unemployed, the age group 15–24 years comprised 43.7%, while the age group 25 to 34, 30.6%. By educational attainment, 20.9% of the unemployed were college graduates, 8.2% were college undergraduates, and 28.2% have completed junior high school. Graduates of junior high school include those high school graduates in the old curriculum" (PSA, 2019). The labor markets in the Philippines and abroad have become very competitive. When parents are confronted with the choice of Universities and Colleges where their children will attend and get a degree, the prospects for future employment carry much weight. Employability, thus, becomes a matter of crucial consideration when schools define their curriculum and their policies on recruitment, entrance, and retention.

Effectiveness of BS Criminal Justice Education Course Curriculum

One of the project components of aligning HEI programs with national development goals is the Job-skills Matching Program. Included in the project is the periodic conduct of graduate tracer studies. The Commission will utilize the results to put up an Annual Higher Education Advisory for parents and students. This will contain information about things such as the most demanded jobs, highest hiring (starting rate) and the types of schools most desired by employers. This will also provide information about state colleges and universities as the basis for budgetary priorities where normative funding is applied. With this research, CHED would be able to formulate package assistance programs to develop and/or enhance higher education programs that would promote the country's global competitiveness.

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In the study of Malaluan et al. (2022), the graduates' knowledge and skills must match the employers' expectations. One of the most common and the most effective ways to determine the status of graduates and the relationship of their educational training with their employment status is the conduct of graduate tracer studies. The ability for graduates to find or create work after higher education is a critical component of a university's reputation and ranking, and a key deciding factor in a student's decision-making process. Moreover, focusing on employability helps universities to attract and retain high quality students and maintain a competitive advantage in the global market. Accordingly, a graduate who leaves the sanctuary of the academy desires to find the best employment out there in the job market (Ruiz et al., 2020). However, a job seeker's desire for the best job is hampered by lack of basic skills relevant to the job, lack of experience, poor communication, and social skills and among others. Competencies learned in college, mode of job search and career-choice related factors can be considered as predictors of employability of graduates. Age, civil status, region of origin, and educational attainment are graduate-related factors that predict graduate employability. Competencies in human relations, communications and information technology serve as advantages to young graduates when looking for employment. Graduates who are recommended by someone and with strong passion for the profession immediately find employment.

In the study of Negro (2008), she revealed that out of 158 respondents, only 67 were employed. Twenty-two were permanent employees, and the rest were temporary or contractual employees. Moreover, it was revealed that employed respondents got their jobs as walk-in applicants while others were recommended by prominent people or had political connections. Furthermore, it shows that the skills relevant to their present occupation as PNP members and credit investigators were investigation, communication, and problem-solving skills. And the main reasons for unemployment were lack of professional eligibility, no job opening in their field of specialization, lack of political connections, and inadequate communication skills. On the other hand, it was revealed in one study that the graduates have poor or inadequate training particularly in the preparation of plan of arrest, search and seizure procedures, law enforcement and crisis management intervention, the art of self-defense and in communication skills (Ruiz et al., 2019). More than one half of the skills and competencies of the respondents who got into police work did not match with the designated positions (Ibutnande, 2009). In the study of Negro and Amparado (2017), they traced the graduates of UCLM, Philippines from 1997 to 2010. Specifically, it ascertained the following: profile of the respondents; reasons for taking the course; employment status of the graduates; status of the employed; strategy used to find the first job; reasons for not being employed; number of graduates who were able to land in a job relevant to the curriculum they had in college; and academic competencies learned in college which were useful on the job. It also determined the relationship between the profile of the graduates and their employment status. Utilizing purposive sampling, this descriptive-correlational design study utilized 281 graduates of the University of Cebu Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue from 1997 to 2010. The study showed that most of the respondents were single, female, residents of the city and from region 7. Most have not taken any professional examinations. The top reason for taking the program was the prospect for immediate employment. The majority of the graduates were employed. Those who were employed belonged to the rank- and-file position in their first job and current job. They were receiving 5,000 to 10,000 Philippine pesos as monthly income. Most belonged to the education sector and worked in the city. They landed their first job through recommendations. The top reason for accepting and staying on the first job was the pay and fringe benefits. The top reason for not being employed and never employed was the absence of a job opportunity. Most of the graduates claimed that they were able to land a job that was relevant to the course that they took in college. The top three competencies learned in school which were useful on the job were communication skills, human relation skills and information technology skills. There was a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents in the aspect of region of origin and their employment status. In conclusion, graduates were employable. The employability of UCLM graduates was influenced by their region of origin.

Quality of Teaching on Students' Employability

According to Leonardi and Chertkovskaya (2017), education represents the most effective investment for enhancing individual capital, leading to improved employability. Continuously acquiring knowledge through learning and practical experiences is a key strategy to enhance employability. Consequently, appropriately structuring educational courses can be an effective approach to optimize the input-output ratio of college students' human capital, thereby significantly influencing their employability prospects. The course setting refers to the teaching plan devised by universities, while course teaching involves the actual implementation of that

plan. The key to effective course teaching lies in elevating the quality of instruction and the dedication of teachers' time and effort. Firstly, the quality of college course teaching is fundamental in enhancing students' employability, with research indicating that stringent quality control leads to increased knowledge acquisition among students. Secondly, when teachers invest more time and energy in teaching, such as helping and timely feedback on assignments, it fosters better teacher-student interaction, stimulating students' interest in learning and promoting independent learning. The greater enthusiasm and time teachers invest in teaching and supporting students, the more knowledge and skills students can acquire. (Zhang et al., 2022)

Furthermore, enhancing the quality of course teaching is vital for boosting college students' employability (Zhang et al., 2022). Therefore, it is essential to strengthen teaching quality control during the implementation of the teaching plan. The course teaching supervision office should actively manage the entire course teaching process, covering faculty development, course implementation, and quality assessment. To achieve this, improvements are required in the course teaching process management, ensuring comprehensive oversight and supervision. From faculty selection to the execution of course teaching, every aspect should be carefully managed to enhance teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Enhancing the teachers' assessment system is also crucial. Giving greater weight to course teaching quality assessment will incentivize teachers to invest more time and effort in their teaching responsibilities. This, in turn, can lead to improved teaching practices and a more engaging learning experience for students. In addition to better management and assessment, promoting diverse teaching methods is essential. Teachers should be encouraged to adopt interactive and student-centered approaches that avoid rigid indoctrination and authoritative teaching styles. By focusing on students' enthusiasm and encouraging their active participation, heuristic teaching methods, like case teaching, can be actively promoted. Such approaches foster a positive and collaborative learning environment, helping to bridge the emotional gap between teachers and students.

In conclusion, strengthening teaching quality control and adopting student-centered teaching methods can significantly impact college students' employability. By fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment, educational institutions can empower students to excel academically and develop the essential skills and knowledge needed for future career success. Furthermore, creating a positive teacher-student relationship through interactive teaching approaches can enhance the overall learning experience and contribute to a more successful educational journey.

Student Activities Engagement on Students' Employability

Participating in club activities is a significant form of practical education for college students, complementing their theoretical education at universities. According to social capital theory, individuals, groups, and organizations acquire tangible and intangible resources through social interactions and connections with others. The theory emphasizes that social capital resources are embedded in interconnected social networks, facilitating access to resources through relationships. College clubs, as social organizations on campus, serve as bridges for communication and exchange, thus representing a form of social capital. Engaging in club activities offers students more opportunities to communicate and exchange ideas, leading to the development of stable social relationships. By participating in these activities, college students can deepen their understanding of theoretical knowledge and apply it to practical skills relevant to their future work. Additionally, involvement in club activities enhances communication skills and fosters a sense of cooperation, as indicated by studies demonstrating that regular participation improves students' communication abilities (Buckley & Lee, 2018). Moreover, club activities, especially those involving college-enterprise cooperation, expose students to the external society and provide insights into job-hunting, corporate recruitment needs, and workplace environments. By actively engaging with society and leveraging the information obtained during the job-hunting process, college students can increase their chances of successful employment.

Learning Environment on Students' Employability

As mentioned by Shresta et al. (2019) in an article that Bloom described the educational or learning environment concept as the conditions, external stimuli and forces which may be physical, social as well as intellectual forces which challenge on the individual and influence students learning outcomes. Also, learning environment is even a strong predictor of learning outcomes of the university. The learning environment extends beyond the physical setting of the classroom and includes various factors that influence students' learning experiences. These factors can include the quality of instruction, interactions with peers and educators, access to resources, institutional support, and the overall atmosphere of the learning environment.

Student Support Services on Students' Employability

Peer support refers to the assistance, encouragement, and camaraderie students receive from their fellow peers. Positive interactions with peers can foster a sense of belonging and social integration within the college community. College is not only about academic learning but also about developing crucial social skills. Peer interactions allow students to practice communication, teamwork, conflict resolution, and leadership skills, which are essential for success in both academic and professional settings. When students feel connected and accepted by their peers, they are more likely to engage in campus activities, participate in discussions, and seek help when needed. Peer support networks can also provide informal mentoring and guidance for new students. Peer mentors can help incoming students navigate the challenges of college life, such as understanding campus resources, managing time effectively, and adapting to the academic workload (Gallop & Bastien, 2019).

Colleges offer employment guidance services to enhance students' success in finding employment. These services include career training courses, career seminars, CV guidance, and more. Nowadays, colleges have established career planning offices and employment guidance centers. The impact of these institutions on college students' employability falls within the research scope of social capital theory. According to social capital theory, individuals are part of social networks, and they have both strong and weak relationships with other members of these networks. Strong relationships in networks are characterized by homogeneity and close emotional ties among members, making them advantageous for job hunting. On the other hand, weak relationships, while less stable, have a broader reach and still play a significant role in job search.

Currently, many college students primarily rely on the Internet or the job market for job-hunting information. While these formal channels provide more job opportunities, they may have specific issues such as lower employment quality, rate, and efficiency. Employment guidance activities serve as an essential means of assisting college students, offering high-quality employment information, and broadening their job-hunting channels. These informal job search channels can provide college students with valuable and high-quality employment opportunities (Pitan & Atiku, 2017; Lu, 2019; Okolie et al., 2020).

II. METHODS

This study utilized quantitative-descriptive research design and was conducted at Saint Paul University Surigao (SPUS), Surigao City, Philippines from August 2022 to May 2023. Seventy-one (71) BS Criminology graduates of SPUS from 2013 to 2020 participated in the study. The research instrument was anchored on the tracer study conducted on education graduates of SPUS which was based also from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 29 s. 2013 (Arbis et al., 2023).

During the data collection stage, the researchers first secured the approval of the study from the University Research and Institutional Development Office. Then, the adapted instrument was sent to graduates by email, Google forms, and social media group chats. The questionnaire was accompanied by a letter informing the participants about the study and assuring them of the data's confidentiality. The researchers retrieved the answered questionnaires. To ensure the protection of the data, the researchers also took some consideration in analyzing the data provided by SPUS. That is, all answers will be based on the existing programs of the college department. Furthermore, the researchers ensured the data collected were used for research purposes only. No part of the study shall be released nor published without prior permission from the university President.

For data analysis, the researchers checked first the normality assumption. Frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to describe the profile of the respondents and graduates' rating of the program. Moreover, t-test and one-way ANOVA were used to test whether significant differences exist on the respondents' rating of their program when grouped based on their employment information.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of the respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, year graduated, location, professional examination(s) passed are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	f	%
Age		
22-26 years old	39	54.93
27-31 years old	27	38.03
32-36 years old	3	4.23
Missing Data	2	2.82
Sex		
Male	47	66.20
Female	23	32.39
Missing Data	1	1.41
Civil Status		
Single	53	74.65
Married	17	23.94
Live-in	1	1.41
Year Graduated		
2013	7	9.86
2014	8	11.27
2015	6	8.45
2016	8	11.27
2017	7	9.86
2018	9	12.68
2019	14	19.72
2020	12	16.90
Location		
City	20	28.17
Municipality	51	71.83
Professional Examination(s) Passed		
Criminology Licensure Examination	49	69.01
NAPOLCOM Examination	1	1.41
Civil Service	2	2.82
Napolcom and Criminology Licensure Examination	7	9.86
Napolcom and Civil Service Examination	1	1.41
None	11	15.49

As to age, 39 or 54.93% aged 22-26 years old, followed by 27 or 38.03% the ages between 27-31 years old, 3 or 4.23% is in the age of 32-36 years old. This implies that majority of the participants were in adulthood which most likely can provide answers efficiently on the objectives of the research study. In terms of sex, out of 70 participants, there are 47 males (66.20%), there are 23 females (33.39). Also, 53 or 74.65% are single, and 17 or 23.94 are married and 1 or 1.41% is in live in civil status across all batches. With regards to year graduated, 7 or 9.86% were from 2013, 8 or 11.27% were from the year 2014, 6 or 8.45% were from 2015, 8 or 11.26% were in 2016, 7 or 9.86% were in the year of 2017, 9 or 12.68% were from the year 2018, 14 or 19.72% were in the year 2019 and 2020 (12 or 16.90%). In terms of the location of residence, 51 or 71.83% resided in the municipality, and 20 or 28.17% lived in the city. As to the professional examinations passed, it can be gleaned that out of 70, 49 or 69.01% of the participants took the Criminology Licensure Examination, then 11 (15.49) answered none, 7 or 9.86% took the Napolcom and Criminology Licensure Examination, the 2 or 2.82% successfully passed the Civil Service and only one for (1.41%) for both NAPOLCOM Examination and NAPOLCOM and Civil Service Examination respectively.

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Table 2. *Employment status of the Graduates and the Reason for unemployment*

Group	f	%
Presently employed		
Yes	49	69.01
No	22	30.99
Reason for Unemployment		
Family Concern	1	6.25
Health-related concerns	1	6.25
Lack of Job Hiring	4	25.00
Did not seek for a job employment	4	25.00
Did not pass Licensure Examination	4	25.00
Lack of work experience	2	12.50

Based on the given results from Table 2 on the employment history of the graduates as to who are currently employed, 49 (69.01%) answered yes, which means they are presently employed. In comparison, 22 (30.99%) answered no. This clearly suggests that more graduates leaned a job and regular income. As to their reasons for unemployment, when the responses were ranked, it revealed that the primary reasons for unemployment are due to lack of job hiring did not seek for a job employment and did not pass the licensure examination with computed frequency of 4 or 25%, followed by lack of experience with computed frequency of 2 or 2.50% and ranked 3, 1 or 6.25 for both health-related concerns and family concern.

Table 3 *Current Employment status, Present occupation, and Affiliation*

Group	f	%
Regular or Permanent		
Temporary	4	7.55
Casual	1	1.89
Contractual	1	1.89
Self-employed	3	5.66
Job Order	1	1.89
Present Occupation		
Police officer	25	53.19
Jail officer	7	14.89
fire officer	7	14.89
Criminology Instructor	3	6.38
Health Augmenter	1	2.13
Freelancer	1	2.13
Administrative Assistant III	1	2.13
Mining	1	2.13
Delivery Boy	1	2.13
Workplace		
Public	45	83.33
Private	9	16.67

Table 3 reveals the current employment status, present occupation, and affiliation. It shows that the participants are currently employed as regular or permanent having the most numbered of population, 48 or 81.13%; 4(7.55%) are employed as temporary, 3 (5.66%) are self-employed, and only 1 for 1 (1.89%) for casual, contractual and job order. In terms of present occupation, 25 (53.19%) out 70 are police officers, 2 (14.89%) are employed as jail officer and fire officer, 3(6.38%) are in the field of criminology instructor, a 1 (2.13%) for

health augments, freelancer, administrative assistant III, mining and delivery boy. As to their affiliation, 45(83.33%) are public personnel and 9(16.67%) are private employees.

Table 4 *First job and Job Relation to the Course*

Group	f	%
Job Relation to the Course		
Yes	43	74.14
No	15	25.86
First Job		
Law enforcement officer	23	48.94
Jail Officer	5	10.64
Contact Tracer	6	12.77
Warehouse man	9	19.15
Marketing Assistant	1	2.13
Traffic Enforcer	1	2.13
PSA employee	1	2.13
DPWH job order	1	2.13

On the other hand, Table 4 shows First job related to the course in college and First job. When the graduates were asked about their first job related with the course, 43 or 74.14 %answered that it was related to their Bachelor of Science in Criminology program, and 15 or 25.86% of them said not.

As to those who answered their first job related to their course 23 or 48.94% worked as Law enforcement officer, 5 or 10.64% worked as jail officer, and only 1 or 2.13% worked as traffic enforcer. As for those who answered otherwise, their course was not related to their first job; it was revealed that 9 or 19.15% worked as warehouse man, 6 or 12.77% worked as contact tracer, followed by 1or 2.13% worked as marketing assistant, 1or 2.13% as PSA employee, and only 1 or 2.13 worked as DPWH job order.

Table 5 *Reason(s) for changing occupation, Reason(s) for accepting the first job*

Group	f	%
Reason for Changing the Job		
Salary and benefits	18	72.00
Proximity to residence	1	4.00
Related to special skills	2	8.00
Career challenge	4	16.00
Reason for Accepting the first Job		
Salary and benefits	26	57.78
Proximity to residence	1	2.22
Related to the course/skills	9	20.00
Career challenge	8	17.78
Work experience	1	2.22

Meanwhile, regarding the reasons for changing occupation, when the responses are ranked, it revealed that the primary reason for the changing the job are salaries and benefits (18 or 72%), career change (4 or 16%), related to special skills (2 or 8%), and proximity to residence (1 or 4%). In terms of reasons for accepting the first job, responses were ranked majority of the answer was related to salary and benefits (26 or 57.78%), followed by related to the course/skills (9 or 20%), the career challenge (8 or 17.78%), and 1 or 2.22% for both work experience and proximity to residence.

Table 6 *Duration of the First Job*

How long did it take to land the first job?	f	%
1 to 6 months	18	42.86
7 to 11 months	4	9.52
1 year to less than 2 years	11	26.19
2 years to less than 3 years	4	9.52
3 years to less than 4 years	5	11.90

Table 6 presents how long it took the participants to land their first job. It can be observed in the above-shown table that 18 or 42.86% took one (1) to six (6) months before landing a job, followed by 11 or 26.19% in one (1) year to less than two (2) years, 5 or 11.90% in three (3) years to less than four (4) years, 4 or 9.52% in seven (7) months to eleven (11) months, and 4 or 9.52% in two (2) years to less than three (3) years.

Table 7. *Graduates rating of their program*

Indicators	M	SD	VI	QD
Quality Teaching				
1. Presented comprehensible explanations; provide understandable examples, additional information, and real-life situation to explain difficult points or lessons	3.64	0.51	STA	VE
2. Maximize student centered learning and encourage class participation and group collaboration.	3.59	0.50	STA	VE
3. Exhibited expertise of the subject or course taught	3.59	0.50	STA	VE
4. Possessed varied, updated pedagogical strategies and instructional content promoting critical analytical thinking skills.	3.57	0.55	STA	VE
5. Provided from feedback and constructive suggestions to improve class performance	3.53	0.56	STA	VE
6. Insured nondiscriminatory remarks and a friendly learning environment	3.56	0.58	STA	VE
Average:	3.58	0.54	STA	VE
Studies Activities Engagement				
1. Joined various student clubs, department, and campus organizations to hone my leadership skills and held a leadership position.	3.44	0.58	STA	VE
2. Became affiliated with the school religious clubs and organizations.	3.46	0.58	STA	VE
3. Actively participated in any religious activity in school.	3.60	0.52	STA	VE
4. I took part in outside and inside school activities and competitions that were of my interest and career related.	3.41	0.67	STA	VE
5. Participated in various seminars, leadership training and symposium	3.46	0.63	STA	VE
Average:	3.48	0.60	STA	VE

Learning Environment

1. Promoted holistic education and life-long skills development.	3.56	0.50	STA	VE
2. Did not condone any form of violence and derogatory remarks amongst students, students to teacher, and teachers to teachers and other faculties.	3.57	0.60	STA	VE
3. Continuously applied a new approach, method, and teaching techniques to improve learning and instructional delivery.	3.58	0.50	STA	VE
4. Adapted to the current trends of the academe and update instructional content, learning materials, and learning modalities.	3.59	0.52	STA	VE
5. Instilled the values of the catholic teachings to become compassionate, competent learners and believers.	3.61	0.52	STA	VE
6. Developed and explored various field activities.	3.58	0.53	STA	VE
7. Offers practical experience as a form of work-based learning and socialization.	3.51	0.53	STA	VE
Average:	3.57	0.53	STA	VE

Student Support Services

1. Library services readily provided learning resources and updated new reading materials necessary for academic references.	3.57	0.50	STA	VE
2. ICT services assisted students having technical difficulties and other ICT - related issues for teaching-learning activities	3.32	0.63	STA	VE
3. College academic services dynamically reviewed learning standards and policies to accelerate learning progress, meet the demands, and cultivate a successful learning engagement.	3.46	0.53	STA	VE
4. Registrar and finance services-maintained confidentiality and secured preventive measures of students' records and financial transactions from a possible security breach	3.45	0.58	STA	VE
5. Laboratory services readily prepared and maintained equipment and apparatus to support immersive and interactive learning activities.	3.43	0.61	STA	VE
Average:	3.45	0.57	STA	VE

Legend:

Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)	Qualitative Description (QD)
3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree (STA)	Very Effective (VE)
2.50 - 3.24	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderately Effective (ME)
1.75 - 2.49	Slightly Agree (SLA)	Less Effective (LE)
1.00 - 1.74	Disagree (D)	Not Effective (NE)

Table 7 presents the Graduates rating of their program in terms of Quality of teaching, Student Activities engagement, Learning environment, and Student support services. The computed grand mean of 3.53 implies that the graduates strongly agree that the quality of teaching, studies activities engagement, learning environment and student support services offered by the Bachelor of Science in Criminology of St. Paul University Surigao are very effective and commendable. The given results further signify that the indicators are recognized and

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practices in the institution to enhance the quality of learning experiences of the graduates that are intensively contribute to the holistic knowledge and skills for their course and future endeavors.

In lieu of the school vision-mission quality policy, St. Paul University Surigao provides quality, Filipino, catholic Paulinian education that is learner focused on a culture of compassionate caring through holistic formation, development of the human resources and upgrading facilities and commitment and involvement of all stakeholders to promote quality and lifelong learning experiences to the learners.

Also, the leadership brand of the University serves as the guiding principle where the students can use as baseline information and foundation of all their school activities gearing towards the achievement of the school's mission and vision that will also be beneficial for future employment.

Developing certain level of maturity of the graduates and sense of responsibility is being held and practiced through the assistance of the Office of Student Affairs where meaningful activities are conducted to help them experience the quality of student life.

Education is the key that will allow many other Sustainable Development Goals (SGDs) to be achieved. When people can get quality education they can break from the cycle of poverty. The success of any education system depends on the quality of both internal and external stakeholders which in turn depends on the effective teaching learning process employed by the teachers. In terms of quality teaching can be seen favorably agreed with an average mean of 3.58. It implies that quality of higher education depends on the quality of teachers who impart the knowledge and skills to the learners of an institution. Teachers play the most crucial role in the development of the education system in imparting and maintaining the standards of higher education (Chakma, 2022).

To promote quality education, the continued implementation of learning outcomes and teacher's professional development duly supported by the St. Paul University Surigao values the training of the educators. It enhances the teacher's confidence in their field of specialization, the necessary skills to advance in their field, denotes more prepared to take on new tasks and opportunities to use transferrable study skills such as organization, timekeeping, and problem solving to manage them successfully.

The second indicator of Student Activities Engagement garnered a computed mean of 3.48. It simply means that the students' passion for connecting with different student's clubs, departments and campus organizations helped hone their leadership skills. Their interest in doing so paved the way for better social and interpersonal skills. Their engagements also influenced their perspective in life having met a lot of people with different backgrounds which in turn was very beneficial in their individual pursuit of endeavors. Research has demonstrated that engaging students in the learning process increases their attention and focus and motivates them to engage in higher-level critical thinking. Student engagement can be seen as the glue that holds together all aspects of student learning growth. Not only does student engagement make teaching itself more fun, engaging and rewarding but it has been shown to have critical impacts on students (Sutton, 2021).

Besides the student's activities engagement, the third indicator states the Learning Environment with mean of 3.57, the graduates strongly agree that the school's learning environment is very effective. It is very crucial in determining where the students would end up in life. It heavily impacts how they conduct themselves in the workplace or in their chosen field. The technique and routine set by the institution allowed students to have a healthy, meaningful, and productive learning environment which allowed them to explore and discover while also keeping the values and experiences they have while in the campus. As mentioned by Shresta et al. (2019) in an article that Bloom described the educational or learning environment concept as the conditions, external stimuli and forces which may be physical, social as well as intellectual forces which challenge on the individual and influence students learning outcomes. Also, learning environment is even a strong predictor of learning outcomes of the university.

On the other hand, student support services must continually complement and uplift the school's mission of providing conducive learning space and environment. With an average of 3.45, it suggests that the students support services of St. Paul University Surigao are very effective, evident and experienced. The services offered

by the institution were of great help to the students' knowing how these aid in the students' ease in learning. Services like the Library, ICT services, College Academic services, Registrar and Finance Services, and Laboratory services. While there are a lot of demands for their chosen field, it is because of these services that the students were relieved that they are well- provided for with the needed resources, assistance, standards and policies, confidentiality, and preparation for the next step of their learning.

Table 8 presents the summary rating of the participants' rating of their program. The overall average score for all the components is 3.52, which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree", indicating a highly positive perception of the entire educational setting. The standard deviation (0.56) suggests a relatively low variation in responses across all components, reaffirming the consistency in participants' opinions.

Table 8. *Summary Table Graduates rating of their program*

Components	M	SD	VI	QD
Quality Teaching	3.58	0.54	SA	VE
Studies Activities Engagement	3.48	0.60	SA	VE
Learning Environment	3.57	0.53	SA	VE
Student Support Services	3.45	0.57	SA	VE
Average	3.52	0.56	SA	VE

As to Quality Teaching component, it garnered the highest mean score of 3.58, indicating that participants, on average, rated the teaching quality positively. The relatively low standard deviation of 0.54 suggests that there was no significant amount of variability in responses. This suggests that participants generally agreed with the presence of quality teaching, and their perceptions were consistent. Several factors could contribute to the positive ratings of teaching quality. These might include engaging teaching techniques, knowledgeable and supportive instructors, well-organized courses, a conducive learning environment, and effective use of technology in the classroom. It could also be an outcome of the institution's commitment to fostering quality education and investing in professional development for instructors (Lazarides & Buchholz, 2019).

As to Studies Activities Engagement component, it has a mean score of 3.48, which also suggests a positive perception of participants regarding their engagement in studies and academic activities. The standard deviation of 0.60 indicates slightly more variability compared to Quality Teaching, but it is still relatively low, implying a considerable level of agreement among respondents. Student engagement is a critical aspect of the learning process. When students are actively engaged in their studies and academic activities, they are more likely to retain information, deepen their understanding, and perform better academically. Positive perceptions of studies engagement suggest that participants find value in their educational experiences and are motivated to be actively involved in their learning.

As to Learning Environment component, it obtained a mean score of 3.57, signifying that participants perceived the learning environment positively. The low standard deviation of 0.53 suggests a high level of consensus among participants, with minimal differences in their opinions about the learning environment. As emphasized, a positive learning environment is crucial for promoting effective learning and student well-being. When students feel comfortable, supported, and safe in their learning environment, they are more likely to be open to new ideas, actively participate in discussions, and take intellectual risks. Understanding the factors that contribute to the positive perception of the learning environment is essential. These factors may include supportive and approachable instructors, well-designed and organized classrooms, access to resources and technology, opportunities for collaboration and interaction, and a sense of inclusivity and respect within the academic community (Jones et al., 2008).

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Lastly, Student Support Services component obtained a mean score of 3.45, indicating a positive perception of the support services provided to students. The standard deviation of 0.57 suggests a relatively low level of variability, implying that participants generally agreed on the effectiveness of student support services. Positive perceptions of student support services are crucial, as effective support services can significantly contribute to student success and overall well-being. When students feel supported and have access to resources that address their needs, they are more likely to overcome challenges, persist in their studies, and achieve their academic goals. Gallop and Bastien (2016) highlighted the importance of peer support in improving understanding of course materials and clarifying difficult concepts. Peer support and networks also determine student's integration and acceptance in higher education institutions which subsequently affects retention and success. Furthermore, understanding which specific support services were most positively perceived by participants can help institutions prioritize and allocate resources effectively. For example, if academic advising received particularly high ratings, it may indicate the importance of investing in comprehensive and accessible advising services.

Generally, the findings are in line with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of quality teaching, engaging academic activities, supportive learning environments, and effective student support services in enhancing the overall educational experience. The results underscore the significance of providing a positive and conducive learning environment for students, ultimately contributing to their academic success and satisfaction.

As seen in Table 9, the respondents' responses in the quality of teaching when grouped according to their present employment status has a p-value of 0.019 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This result means that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. In addition, this means that there is a significant variation in the responses on the quality of teaching when grouped according to the respondent's present employment status. Furthermore, the significant variation in the responses indicates that the respondents' present employment status plays a role in shaping their perceptions of teaching quality. In other words, employees with different employment statuses have distinct views and opinions about the quality of teaching they experience.

The finding that employment status provides different perceptions of teaching quality suggests that the working conditions and job security of respondents might influence how they perceive the teaching they receive. According to Leonardi and Chertkovskaya (2017), education plays a critical role in improving employability by equipping individuals with relevant skills, knowledge, and qualifications that employers seek in potential candidates. As industries evolve, employees must stay abreast of new developments to remain employable. For instance, those who are permanently employed may feel more invested in the institution's success and might view the teaching quality more positively. On the other hand, those employed on a contractual basis, who may have concerns about their job stability or benefits, might have a more critical view of teaching quality (Abd Majid et. al, 2020).

Table 9. Test of Significant Difference of BSCRIM graduates' rating of their academic program when grouped according to their employment status.

Profile Variables	Dependent Variables	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Present Employment Status	Quality Teaching	0.019	Reject H_0	Significant
	Studies Activities Engagement	0.574	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Learning Environment	0.235	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
Present Occupation	Student Support Services	0.771	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Quality Teaching	0.491	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Studies Activities Engagement	0.205	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Learning Environment	0.390	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Student Support Services	0.710	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
Workplace	Quality Teaching	0.147	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Studies Activities Engagement	0.796	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Learning Environment	0.167	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Student Support Services	0.952	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Quality Teaching	0.653	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Studies Activities Engagement	0.091	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
First Job	Learning Environment	0.437	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Student Support Services	0.883	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
Months/ Years needed to land in first job	Quality Teaching	0.806	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Studies Activities Engagement	0.496	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Learning Environment	0.595	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant
	Student Support Services	0.201	Do not reject H_0	Not Significant

Zhang et. al (2022) highlighted the crucial role that quality course teaching plays in enhancing students' employability. When students receive high-quality instruction, they are better equipped with the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to succeed in their chosen careers. These results may have practical implications for educational institutions and policymakers. Understanding that employment status can influence perceptions of teaching quality can help in developing targeted strategies to improve teaching experiences for different employee groups. Institutions may need to consider how job security, benefits, and overall job satisfaction impact teaching effectiveness and, consequently, the learning experiences of students.

Accordingly, employability comprises four dimensions, namely, understanding of subjects, fundamental skills, self-efficacy, and metacognition. This study introduced a comprehensive framework for college students' employability, encompassing professional knowledge and skills, learning aptitude, adaptability, practical proficiency, effective communication, teamwork capability, information acquisition capacity, and career planning proficiency. Learning ability refers to students' capacity to acquire new knowledge, adapt to changing circumstances, and continually improve their skills. A strong learning ability is essential in a rapidly evolving job market, where individuals need to be adaptable and open to continuous learning.

Table 10. Overall rating of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curricular program

Overall rating of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curricular program	<u>M</u>	SD	VI	QD
1. Conduct criminological research on crimes, crime causation, victims, and offenders to include deviant behavior.	3.62	0.49	SA	VE
2. Demonstrate competence and broad understanding in law enforcement administration, public safety, criminal justice and human rights.	3.67	0.47	SA	VE
3. Internalize the concepts of human rights and victim welfare.	3.61	0.52	SA	VE
4. Utilize criminalistics or forensic science in the investigation and detection of crime.	3.62	0.49	SA	VE
5. Apply the principles and jurisprudence of criminal law, evidence and criminal procedure.	3.68	0.50	SA	VE
6. Ensure offenders' welfare and development for their reintegration to the community.	3.61	0.52	SA	VE
7. Collaborate effectively and independently in multi-disciplinary and multi-cultural teams.	3.54	0.53	SA	VE
8. Engage in lifelong learning and understanding of the need to keep abreast on the development in the field of criminology and criminalistics.	3.64	0.48	SA	VE
9. Exhibit sense of responsibility, accountability, integrity, high moral values and fear of God as an effective and efficient community leader.	3.65	0.48	SA	VE
Average:	3.63	0.50	SA	VE

Table 10 shows the overall rating of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curricular program. St. Paul University Surigao has been remarkably continuing shaping graduates to become academically inclined and exhibit the Christ centered, competent responsible persons in the service of the society in generating employment in the public and private sectors. It can be inferred from Table 4 that the graduate's standpoint on their college learning experiences as to the program has significantly helped and is very effective with an average mean of 3.63.

The assurance of the effective implementation of academic programs in higher education are established when the curriculum desired outcomes skills and competencies are emphasized and demonstrated as expected to the learners after they have finished their baccalaureate studies. The following attributes such as professionally competent graduates, who can deliver efficient and effective services in crime prevention, crime detection and investigation, law enforcement and criminal law research. The holistic education provided by the institution molds the graduates getting ready for the labor force.

As highlighted on the study of Ederio et al. (2021), St Paul University Surigao is filled by its emphasis on providing holistic education that cultivates the learners cognitive, social, emotional, and spiritual dimensions and exudes excellence for the stewardship and service of the Filipino men. And more significantly it is the livewires that promotes the Filipino heritage and inclusivity to different world views and cultures in the present era of the globalization movement. Furthermore, these findings indicated that effective implementation of the curriculum is well-proved by teachers as an essential element in the classroom and leadership of administration in driving and streamlining educational services human resource development, enhanced teaching training, and productivity. Teachers, as curriculum implementers, still the most vital element in the implementation of the curriculum and should be exposed and trained to different professional training as it potentially affects and

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reforms curriculum practices. Moreover, Ederio et al. (2021) emphasized that effective leadership in implementing academic programs in higher education institutions ensures optimum productivity and influences peer relationships, collegial work, and mobilizing support.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study aimed to trace and determine the employment status of Criminology graduates from 2013 to 2020. This research sought to find out the graduate's rating of their program as to Quality Teaching, Studies Activities Engagement, Learning Environment, and Student Support Services as well as the significant difference when they are grouped by age, sex, civil status, year graduated, current address, and professional examinations passed. The researcher's utilized descriptive design utilizing the questionnaire adopted from the CHED tracer study and administered the tool to all Paulinian criminology students who graduated from 2013 to 2020 using google form. The data were retrieved, tallied, and interpreted. Based on the results of the study, the following findings were formulated:

1. As to the profile of the respondents, the most number was 39 (54.93%) from the age bracket of 22-26 years old; however, the least number was from missing data with 2 or 2.82 percent. As to sex, male had the highest number of participants comprising 47 or 66.20 percent, while female had the least number with 23 or 32.69 percent. As to civil status, the highest number of participants were single with 53 or 74.65 percent while the least was live-in with 1 or 1.41 percent. As to the year graduated, 2019 had the highest number of participants comprising the 14 or 19.72 percent, while the least was 2015 with 6 or 8.45 percent. As to current address, the greatest number of participants were from Municipality with 51 or 71.83 percent while the least were from City with 20 or 28.17 percent. As to professional examinations passed, the highest were Criminology Licensure Examination with 49 or 69.01 percent while they were NAPOLCOM and NAPOLCOM Civil Service Examination both with 1 or 1.41 percent.
2. As to the graduates rating of their programs, the respondents answered Strongly Agree on quality teaching which obtained the average mean of 3.58 and a standard deviation of 0.54 with a qualitative description of Very effective; Strongly Agree on studies activities engagement which obtained an average mean of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 0.60 with a qualitative description of Very Effective; Strongly Agree on learning environment which obtained an average mean of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 0.53 with a qualitative description of Very Effective; and Strongly Agree on student support services which obtained an average mean of 3.45 and a standard deviation of 0.57 with a qualitative description of Very Effective.
3. As to the overall rating of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curricular program, of all the indicators, indicator 5 obtained the highest mean of 3.68 and a standard deviation of 0.50 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree with a qualitative description of Very Effective; while indicator 7 obtained the lowest mean of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 0.53 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree with a qualitative description of Very Effective.
4. As to the significant difference, there was no significant difference when the respondents were grouped according to their profile, except for the quality teaching and present employment status.

Hence, majority of the respondents answered Strongly Agree on the graduates rating of their program such as Quality Teaching, Studies Activities Engagement, Learning Environment, and Student Support Services. For Quality Teaching, the participants strongly agree that the teachers at St. Paul University Surigao presented comprehensible explanations; provide understandable examples, additional information, and real-life situation to explain difficult points or lessons. For Studies Activities Engagement, the participants strongly agree that they actively participated in any religious activity in school. For Learning Environment, the participants strongly agree that the university instilled in the students the values of catholic teachings to become compassionate, competent learners and believers. For Student Support Services, the participants strongly agree that library services readily provided learning resources and updated new reading materials necessary for academic references.

Guided by the findings and conclusions of the study, the following concern was forwarded as recommendations:

1. The school administration should provide adequate professional advancement to the teachers to continuously utilize innovative techniques and strategies that could aid in the students' learning and compete with the advancement and progression of today's pursuit of knowledge globally.
2. The administrators should help cultivate good governance and collaborative leadership to emphasize human resources platforms and constant professional development and training to sustain the excellent learning engagement.
3. Upgrade the existing quality of teaching, maximize student's activity engagement, develop the learning environment, and elevate student support services to provide a sustainable learning advancement.
4. Further studies should include employability of SPUS Criminology graduates from present going 5-10 years back.

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